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WHEATBIOME

Unraveling the potential of the wheat microbiome for the development of healthier, more sustainable and resilient wheat-derived food & feed products

DELIVERABLE D7.1 COMMUNICATION, DISSEMINATION AND EXPLOITATION PLAN

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Dissemination Level		
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PU	Public	X
PP	Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services)	
RE	Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services)	
SEN	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)	

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2. ABBREVIATIONS AND ACRONYMS

List of abbreviations and acronyms:

Acronyms and abbreviations	Description
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
PM	Policy Makers
R&I	Research and Innovation
SC	Scientific Community
WP	Work Package
KOM	Kick-Off Meeting
PR	Press Release
SEO	Search Engine Optimisation
GA	Grant Agreement
CTA	Contactica

3. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This document outlines the communication, dissemination, and exploitation strategy for the **WHEATBIOME** project, designed to engage a diverse range of stakeholders, including agricultural professionals, microbiome researchers, policymakers, the food and feed industry, and the general public. The key components of this strategy are as follows:

- **WHEATBIOME** will participate in industry and scientific events to present the project's progress and results. These engagements will foster networking opportunities and help establish collaborations with key stakeholders in the agrifood and microbiome sectors.
- The project's **website** will serve as a central hub for sharing updates, achievements, and resources. Regular posts will ensure stakeholders are informed in real time about the project's advancements, case studies, and research outputs.
- **Social media platforms**, such as Twitter and LinkedIn, will be used to engage with broader audiences. Posts will share project milestones, news, and key developments in microbiome research and sustainable food systems.
- **Newsletters** will be periodically issued to provide concise updates on WHEATBIOME's activities and breakthroughs, ensuring that stakeholders remain connected to the project's evolution.
- **WHEATBIOME** will also produce **informative materials** like brochures, infographics, and videos aimed at non-technical audiences, explaining the project's goals, the importance of microbiomes in food systems, and its contributions to sustainable agriculture.

Moreover, the project seeks to actively form partnerships with key European initiatives and stakeholders, ensuring knowledge sharing and the dissemination of best practices. **WHEATBIOME** will strengthen its outreach by participating in events and leveraging institutional relationships to maximize its visibility across multiple sectors.

In summary, **WHEATBIOME's** communication, dissemination, and exploitation plan is designed to effectively reach and engage a wide variety of stakeholders, ensuring broad visibility and adoption of the project's results within the scientific community and beyond.

4. INTRODUCTION

WHEATBIOME is the acronym for the project called *Unravelling the potential of the wheat microbiome for the development of healthier, more sustainable and resilient wheat-derived food & feed products*. This European project wants **to unlock all the potential of wheat crops** with strong collaboration between academia, industry, food system actors and governmental authorities.

The project will contribute to the understanding of the role of the wheat microbiome on sustainable development by undertaking cutting-edge research. With **2 case studies** and a **lab-scale demonstrator**, the consortium will try to **understand the effect of biotic/abiotic factors on wheat microbiomes**. In addition, novel foods and feeds will be developed by **learning about new fermentation capacities** within indigenous wheat microbiomes.

Furthermore, **WHEATBIOME** will study **the role of microbial fermentations in the quality of foods and feeds**, and recirculate wheat by-products with the goal of **reducing food waste**. The **interactions between wheat and animal or human microbiota** will be determined and its effects assessed. Also, **sustainable farming practices for resilient and nutritious wheat crops** will be delivered and **perception of food system actors and citizens about microbiomes** within food systems will be analysed.

In 2020, wheat was the grain with largest acreage and the European Union was the world major producer of this important crop. That is why the project wants to release all of its potential.

Wheat has been a key crop for human development thanks to its low growing requirements and because it's considered as a well-known source of protein and energy. But **food and crop production are facing several challenges nowadays**, due to factors like demographic growth or climate change, among many others. Also, according to the

European Commission, **65% of current European Union soils are expected to be damaged**, which makes soil restoration a priority aligned both to the [EU's Green Deal](#) and the [Farm2Fork Strategy](#).

Therefore, **sustainability in the food production and value chain is key**, from many perspectives, including being able to feed an ever-growing number of people, maintaining soil and crops qualities, delivering healthy and nutritious products, protecting biodiversity and contributing to climate resilience of Europe.

Currently, 1 trillion different microbial species inhabit the Earth, from which soil and plant microbial communities are really important. Advancements on the discovery and characterization of novel microorganisms are necessary to identify novel microbiome-based products and processes, and to boost sustainable food systems. However, more studies and bio- characterization of soil and plant microbiomes are needed: **only 1% of the bacteria in environmental habitats are subject of cultivation at the moment.**

The challenge for the Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation of the **WHEATBIOME** project lays on the different audiences that the project wants to reach. This can be tackled through different channels and messages, as well as a tailor-made strategy to impact all the right audiences at the right stage of the project.

The tools and details will be **combined and used properly throughout the project** aiming to achieve the maximum visibility for each specific target group. Along this communication and dissemination plan, strategies, messages and channels will be explained to plan how to address specific audiences and reach the project goals. All projects have the need of a strong communication, but **those aiming to reach the general public need to double efforts** for their message to impact the maximum number of people. Addressing general public is a challenge that **WHEATBIOME** can overcome through **strong messages and different channels and approaches**. For the most specialized audience, dissemination tools and approaches can be used.

4.1. Context of WP7

The main goal of **Work Package 7 (WP7)** of the **WHEATBIOME** project is to develop an effective strategy for the **communication, dissemination, and exploitation** of the project's results, ensuring that the innovations and advancements in leveraging the wheat microbiome reach a wide range of target audiences. These audiences include key actors in the food system, academic researchers, policymakers, and the general public.

WP7 will focus on creating a coherent framework that ensures all communication activities present a strong and consistent project image, facilitating knowledge transfer and ensuring that the project's message on sustainability and food health is clear and accessible. Part of this strategy involves training food system actors in the use of microorganisms as bioregulators to produce sustainable and healthy food products.

Additionally, WP7 will **foster synergies** with other European projects, enabling knowledge exchange between various stakeholders across different European regions. The work package will also develop an **exploitation plan** for intellectual property management and potential business models, ensuring that the project's results can be practically applied and have a long-term impact on the agrifood sector.

In summary, WP7 is designed to ensure the **wide dissemination** of the project's outcomes, promote their adoption across the food value chain, and encourage collaboration and innovation within the wheat microbiome research landscape.

4.2. Objectives of task 7.1

The Grant Agreement (GA) contemplates that a detailed Dissemination and Communication Strategy will be produced at the beginning of the project (M6), based on the preliminary indications given in Section 2.2 and collaboration with the consortium. Contactica (CTA) will oversee the execution of various dissemination and communication activities as outlined in the tables of Section 2.2. At a scientific level, each partner will assume responsibility for attending, participating in, and, when applicable, organizing specific scientific events and publications.

The primary objective of the dissemination strategy for the **WHEATBIOME** project is to effectively communicate the project's results and innovations to a broad range of stakeholders, ensuring the widespread adoption and impact of its key findings. To achieve this, **WHEATBIOME** will implement a multistep and multichannel approach, tailoring information to meet the specific interests and needs of each target group. Information will be tailored to meet the specific needs and interests of each group.

This strategy contributes towards achieving the project's specific objectives by ensuring that communication activities effectively inform and promote the **WHEATBIOME** project and its outcomes to diverse audiences, including the media and the general public. It aims to showcase how EU funding plays a crucial role in addressing societal challenges.

The Communication Plan will focus on the following objectives:

- (1) Provide a main framework for all communications, dissemination and exploitation activities, ensuring coherence, and presenting a strong project image to external stakeholders, target audiences (actors of the food system) and to the general public (citizens).
- (2) Train actors of the food systems in the proper use of microorganism as bioregulator and producers of new sustainable and healthy food products.
- (3) Enable synergies between European projects and facilitate knowledge exchange between different stakeholders in different European regions.
- (4) Develop an exploitation plan for intellectual property management and possible business plans.

5. TARGET AUDIENCES

To optimize the impact of the communication, dissemination, and exploitation efforts within the **WHEATBIOME** project, it is crucial to tailor key messages and actions to the diverse target audiences. This involves considering factors such as their level of knowledge, interests, geographical location, and specific roles within the food system. By adapting communication strategies to these variables, the project ensures that its findings and innovations reach the right stakeholders effectively.

The **WHEATBIOME** project primarily targets professionals and stakeholders within the **agrifood sector** as its main audience, including actors involved in food production, agricultural technology, and microbiome research. The project’s goal is to engage stakeholders who are crucial for adopting sustainable practices in wheat cultivation and microbiome applications, promoting healthier and more resilient food systems. These key audiences include **farmers, agronomists, microbiologists, food manufacturers, and nutrition experts**, all of whom play a role in enhancing the sustainability and nutritional value of wheat-derived products.

In addition, the project seeks to involve **policymakers, regulatory bodies**, and **European institutions**, aiming to influence agricultural policies and align with broader strategies such as the EU Green Deal and Farm2Fork. The **scientific community** is also a key audience, with researchers in microbiomes, soil health, and fermentation processes targeted through workshops, scientific publications, and collaborative initiatives.

Secondary audiences include the **general public**, especially consumers interested in sustainable food choices, **students**, and **educational institutions**. Engaging these groups through clear and accessible messages will help raise awareness about the importance of microbiomes in food systems and promote sustainable consumption practices.

By tailoring its messages and dissemination activities to meet the needs and interests of these groups, **WHEATBIOME** ensures that its innovations are understood and adopted by those who can drive the transition towards a more sustainable and resilient food system.

Table 1: Target Audiences for Wheatbiome results

Audience Type	Stakeholder Category	Description
Primary	Agrifood Sector Professionals	Includes farmers, agronomists, microbiologists, and food manufacturers involved in sustainable wheat production and microbiome applications. They play a key role in adopting innovative

		practices to enhance food system sustainability and resilience.
Primary	Researchers & Academia	Researchers specializing in microbiomes, soil health, and fermentation processes. They contribute to advancing scientific understanding and applying WHEATBIOME’s findings in other related research areas.
Primary	Policymakers & Regulatory Bodies	EU institutions, agricultural policy influencers, and regulatory bodies interested in supporting sustainable farming practices aligned with the EU Green Deal and Farm2Fork strategies.
Primary	Food System Actors	Professionals across the food system, including dietitians, nutritionists, and food safety associations. These stakeholders influence how microbiome innovations are integrated into food production and safety practices.
Secondary	General Public & Consumers	Informed consumers interested in sustainable, healthy food choices. Raising awareness of microbiome benefits in food and feed products is key for broader adoption.
Secondary	Educational Institutions & Students	Universities, schools, and students involved in food science, agriculture, and sustainability studies. Engaging these groups builds awareness and

		knowledge for future food system innovations.
Secondary	Industry Associations	Organizations and associations representing the food and feed sectors, animal feed, or sustainable food movements. They help disseminate WHEATBIOME's innovations within their networks.
Secondary	Media & Communication Platforms	Media outlets, scientific journals, and communication channels that promote WHEATBIOME's results and raise public and professional awareness.

In addition to these groups, the **WHEATBIOME** project is actively engaging stakeholders within the agrifood and microbiome research communities, forming a collaborative network of experts and practitioners. This network will facilitate the exchange of knowledge and specialized expertise, helping to advance the implementation of innovative microbiome-based solutions aimed at improving the sustainability and resilience of wheat production. Through collaborations with European institutions, industry partners, and scientific researchers, **WHEATBIOME** will contribute to the development of healthier and more sustainable food and feed products, while promoting environmentally friendly farming practices

6. KEY MESSAGES

The **WHEATBIOME** project aims to effectively disseminate its results to a broad range of stakeholders, including professionals in the agrifood sector, microbiome researchers, research institutions, academia, policymakers, and the general public.

Through targeted communication and outreach activities, the project seeks to share knowledge on the innovative use of wheat microbiomes to enhance sustainable food and

feed production, highlighting their potential positive impacts on food system resilience and health. The dissemination strategy, aligned with Horizon Europe guidelines, will promote the widespread adoption of microbiome-based practices and solutions within the agrifood industry.

Key messages will focus on the project’s scientific achievements and their contributions to sustainability, with regular updates provided to stakeholders to ensure transparency and continuous engagement. Effective dissemination will ensure broad access to the project’s outputs, encourage collaboration across sectors, and contribute to the establishment of best practices in promoting healthier and more sustainable food systems.

Table 2: Key Messages.

Audience Type	Stakeholder Category	Description
Primary	Agrifood Sector Professionals	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How microbiomes can improve wheat sustainability, resilience, and food quality. • Practical applications of wheat microbiomes to enhance productivity and reduce environmental impact. • Benefits of using microorganisms as bioregulators in sustainable agricultural practices.
Primary	Researchers & Academia	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Advances in microbiome research and their impact on food and feed systems. • New scientific insights into wheat microbiome interactions and fermentation processes. • Opportunities for collaboration and knowledge exchange with other scientific projects.
Primary		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Contributions of WHEATBIOME to the EU Green Deal and Farm2Fork strategies.

	<p>Policymakers & Regulatory Bodies</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The role of microbiomes in enhancing food security and reducing waste. • How wheat microbiomes can drive policy changes toward more sustainable food systems.
<p>Primary</p>	<p>Food System Actors</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Role of microbiomes in improving food quality and safety. • Sustainable solutions for food production using wheat microbiomes. • Importance of integrating microbiome-based innovations to meet consumer demands for healthy and sustainable food.
<p>Secondary</p>	<p>General Public & Consumers</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The importance of microbiomes in ensuring healthier, more sustainable food products. • How WHEATBIOME’s findings can contribute to a more eco-friendly and nutritious food supply. • Practical steps consumers can take to support sustainable food choices.
<p>Secondary</p>	<p>Educational Institutions & Students</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Opportunities to learn about cutting-edge research in microbiomes and sustainability. • The role of wheat microbiomes in advancing future food systems. • Educational resources and case studies from the project to support learning.

<p>Secondary</p>	<p>Industry Associations</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Potential for microbiome innovations to revolutionize the food and feed sectors. • Collaboration opportunities to integrate WHEATBIOME results into broader industry practices. • Long-term benefits of sustainable microbiome-based solutions for the agrifood sector.
<p>Secondary</p>	<p>Media & Communication Platforms</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Updates on the latest research and breakthroughs in microbiome science. • The societal and environmental impact of WHEATBIOME’s innovations. • Stories and content promoting the project’s milestones and successes in sustainable agriculture.

In addition to the substantial scientific and technological progress made in understanding soil health and enhancing crop resilience, the **WHEATBIOME** project will also establish and implement targeted dissemination and communication strategies. These initiatives aim to foster widespread awareness of sustainable agricultural practices and promote the adoption of innovative solutions that can significantly improve wheat production. By engaging with a diverse array of stakeholders—ranging from farmers and agricultural professionals to policymakers and the general public— **WHEATBIOME** seeks to expedite the implementation of its findings, ultimately contributing to a more sustainable and resilient agricultural system.

7. DISSEMINATION STRATEGY

The primary goal of the **WHEATBIOME** project's dissemination strategy is to generate interest among relevant stakeholders by forming inclusive groups across various sectors within agriculture and soil health. This approach aims to engage wheat producers, agricultural associations, research institutions, academia, policymakers, and the general

public. Through targeted dissemination, the project seeks to facilitate knowledge transfer regarding its innovative solutions for enhancing soil health and crop resilience while highlighting the positive impacts of these technologies.

To ensure these objectives are achieved, the WHEATBIOME's dissemination strategy will align with the Open Science practices outlined in Article 17 of the Grant Agreement.

The dissemination plan will progress through three phases, each adapting to the evolution of **WHEATBIOME**:

- 1. Awareness Phase (M1-M12):** In this initial stage, the focus will be on establishing a community of stakeholders and identifying suitable channels for dissemination. Activities will aim to raise awareness about the **WHEATBIOME** project and its objectives among key groups, including farmers, agricultural representatives, academic institutions, governmental bodies, and relevant associations. Efforts will be made to determine the most effective communication channels and build strong relationships with stakeholders from the outset.
- 2. Scientific Cooperation Phase (M6-M36):** During this phase, the emphasis will be on fostering collaboration with similar projects and initiatives while ensuring that research findings are accessible to targeted audiences. Activities such as participation in agricultural conferences, publication of articles in relevant scientific journals, and organization of workshops will be conducted to share knowledge and engage with the scientific community in the fields of sustainable agriculture and soil health. Additionally, partnerships with professional associations and networks will be established to enhance the impact and dissemination of project results.
- 3. Exploitation-Focused Phase (M24-M36):** In this advanced stage of the project, particular attention will be given to supporting the actual exploitation of results by target users. This will involve activities such as developing market strategies and identifying knowledge transfer opportunities to ensure that **WHEATBIOME** outcomes are effectively implemented in practice. Further efforts will be made to engage end users and ensure that project results align with their needs and

expectations. Opportunities will also be sought to showcase project achievements at prominent agricultural events and to establish strategic partnerships with key stakeholders in the fields of agriculture and soil health.

Table 3: Communication and Dissemination KPIs

Tool/Channel	Stakeholder category	KPIs/target
Website	All	<u>3.000</u>
Social media	Key stakeholders,	Twitter <u>200</u>
	Multiplicators	LinkedIn <u>200</u>
Communication campaigns	Multiplicators	<u>7</u>
Newsletter	Key stakeholders,	<u>4</u>
	Multiplicators	
Press releases	All	<u>4</u>
Videos	<u>All</u>	<u>3</u>
		<u>200</u> per video
Brochure	All	Handed <u>1.000</u>
		Downloaded <u>300</u>
Practice abstracts	Key stakeholders,	<u>50</u>
	Multiplicators	
Scientific publications	All	<u>20</u>
Scientific guidelines and best practices	Key stakeholders,	<u>7</u>
	Multiplicators	
Conferences	Key stakeholders,	<u>30</u>
	Multiplicators	<u>30</u>
Trade fairs	Key stakeholders,	<u>10</u>
	Multiplicators	
Other events	Key stakeholders,	<u>8</u>
	Multiplicators	
Trainings	Multiplicators	<u>10</u>
Workshops	Key stakeholders,	<u>5</u>
	Multiplicators	
Field trips	Key stakeholders	<u>2</u>
		<u>20</u>
Clustering activities	Key stakeholders,	<u>10</u>
	Multiplicators	
Contact with public bodies	Key stakeholders	<u>10</u>

The **WHEATBIOME** project is adopting an "Open Access" (OA) approach, which is essential for fostering collaboration, sharing tools, and effectively disseminating knowledge. This approach is reflected in the dissemination plan through the following actions:

I. Open-access scientific publications:

Implementing an open access (OA) policy for peer-reviewed papers will provide numerous benefits. It promotes transparency in the research process, encourages collaboration within the scientific community, and enhances research efficiency by enabling the sharing, reproduction, and replication of findings. The project aims to publish approximately 20 peer-reviewed scientific papers, with completion by ongoing impact assessed through citation counts. The commitment to OA is reinforced by the active participation of the **WHEATBIOME** consortium, who will follow the OA practices mentioned in Article 17 of the GA:

- Upload a machine-readable electronic copy of the published or peer-reviewed version in a trusted repository at the latest by the time of publication.
- Ensure the deposited publication is accessible immediately under the latest Creative Commons Attribution Licence (CC BY) or similar, with allowances for non-commercial and non-derivative options for monographs.
- Include details in the repository on any additional tools or data needed to validate the publication's conclusions.
- Open metadata under a Creative Commons Public Domain Dedication (CC 0) or equivalent, following FAIR principles.
- Publish metadata under a Creative Commons Public Domain Dedication (CC 0), adhering to FAIR principles, and include essential details such as publication authorship, funding information, project details, licensing terms, and persistent identifiers.
- Only fees for publication in full open-access venues qualify for reimbursement.

II. Policy Feedback:

WHEATBIOME will provide informed feedback to policymakers based on the project's outcomes and research findings. This feedback will assist in the development of policies

related to sustainable wheat production, soil health, and biodiversity conservation within agricultural systems. By sharing insights from our research, we aim to shape regulations that encourage the adoption of innovative practices and technologies in the agricultural sector, contributing to food security and environmental resilience.

III. Cooperation Strategy:

The **WHEATBIOME** project will establish synergies with other initiatives funded under Horizon Europe, particularly those focusing on sustainable agriculture and food systems. These collaborations aim to enhance synergies and broaden the impact of **WHEATBIOME** within the evolving landscape of sustainable practices in food production, ensuring a collective approach to addressing challenges in the agricultural sector.

IV. Stakeholder Management and Engagement:

WHEATBIOME will actively engage stakeholders at various levels, including farmers, agricultural organizations, researchers, policymakers, and the public, to ensure their involvement in project activities and to gather valuable feedback on project progress and outcomes. This engagement will involve organizing stakeholder meetings, workshops, and events to facilitate dialogue and collaboration, ensuring that the project aligns with the needs and expectations of all involved parties and promotes a holistic approach to sustainable wheat production.

8. TOOLS AND CHANNELS

The current and upcoming communication activities for the **WHEATBIOME** project aim to effectively convey the project's goals and outcomes to a diverse range of audiences in clear and accessible language. Under the leadership of the project coordinator and with the support of the consortium, a consistent communication strategy will be implemented. This strategy will be founded on a comprehensive set of methods and tools designed to showcase the project's success and its significant relevance, presenting information in a manner that is easily understood by all stakeholders.

By utilizing a wide array of communication channels, the project consortium will enhance awareness and understanding of how research and innovation within **WHEATBIOME** can

address sustainability challenges and improve agricultural practices. The project will articulate the societal benefits of innovative approaches to soil health and crop resilience while increasing visibility and awareness of the crucial role that Horizon Europe and EU-funded research play in achieving ambitious EU sustainability goals.

The **WHEATBIOME** communication strategy will ensure that the communication plan is regularly reviewed and aligned with evolving needs and future prospects. Key elements of the strategic communication plan include:

- **Development of a Visual Identity:** Creation of a project logo, slogan, and branding for all communication materials to establish a cohesive identity.
- **Dedicated Website:** Operation of a user-friendly website accessible throughout the project duration and for a period following its completion, providing up-to-date information and resources.
- **Social Media Engagement:** Active utilization of social media platforms such as LinkedIn, Twitter, and YouTube, initiated early in the project timeline to reach a wider audience.
- **Biannual Newsletters:** Distribution of newsletters every six months, offering updates on project progress and key findings to stakeholders.
- **Press Releases and Media Kits:** Issuance of press releases and relevant materials to engage media outlets and journalists, enhancing public awareness of **WHEATBIOME's** innovations.
- **Participation in Industry Events:** Presentation of project outcomes at agricultural innovation events, networking opportunities, and industry exhibitions to showcase achievements and foster collaboration.
- **Engagement with External Networks:** Building connections with external groups beyond the project's direct scope, leveraging the existing networks of consortium partners for broader dissemination.
- **In-House Presentations:** Conducting presentations for current collaborators to stimulate discussions on the potential applications and expansions of **WHEATBIOME** results across various sectors.

Additionally, tailored materials such as brochures, case studies, and testimonials will be developed to engage the general public, supported by audio-visual content. Media relations will be nurtured to involve journalists and bloggers in disseminating project updates via social media releases.

In accordance with Article 17 of the GA, all communication activities and publications associated with the project, including the project website, must acknowledge EU support and display the European flag (emblem) and funding statement. The emblem must remain distinct and separate from other visual marks, brands, or text, ensuring that it is prominently displayed alongside other logos of beneficiaries or sponsors. Furthermore, a disclaimer will be provided, translated into local languages where appropriate, to clearly communicate the project's EU funding.

“Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or [name of the granting authority]. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.”

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8.1. PROJECT IDENTITY

A distinctive project identity has been established for the **WHEATBIOME** initiative to create a strong visual brand presence. This identity comprises a set of templates designed to enhance project visibility over time. It includes the creation of a project logo and a comprehensive style guide. These components are applied uniformly across various communication materials, such as the project website, PowerPoint presentations, Word documents, posters, and reports.

A strong and recognizable brand is essential for any project, institution, or company to enhance visibility and facilitate effective communication. For the **WHEATBIOME** project, branding plays a vital role in achieving communication objectives and ensuring that stakeholders can easily identify and engage with the initiative. By fostering a cohesive identity, **WHEATBIOME** aims to strengthen its outreach efforts and promote sustainable agricultural practices effectively.

8.1.1. Project Name

As stated before, the project's name is an **acronym** formed putting together two words: wheat and microbiome, creating the acronym **WHEATBIOME** from the title *Unravelling*

the potential of the wheat microbiome for the development of healthier, more sustainable and resilient wheat-derived food & feed products.

This complete title must always be **written between quotation marks** when used for communication purposes and always **written in capital letters**.

8.1.2. Visual Identity

The visual identity of **WHEATBIOME** encompasses the logo and the project name, serving as the primary means of presenting the project visually. A compelling visual identity creates a strong first impression and helps stakeholders remember the project through various communication materials.

To establish a cohesive visual identity, two critical elements must be defined:

Figure 1: WHEATBIOME Logo.

Colors: A specific color palette has been chosen to reflect the project's mission and values. These colors should be consistently applied across all documents, PowerPoint presentations, and communication materials related to **WHEATBIOME**. Consistent use of these colors will reinforce brand recognition and create a unified visual presence.

Figure 2: Colors codes.

- **Typography:** A set of fonts has been selected to complement the project logo and enhance readability across all communication materials. Consistent typography will ensure that **WHEATBIOME** materials are professional and cohesive.

Bahnshrift Light Semi Condensed

Aa Bb Cc Dd Ee Ff Gg Hh Ii Jj Kk Ll Mm Nn Ññ Oo Pp Qq Rr Ss Tt Uu Vv Ww Xx Yy Zz 1234567890 / * - + = ¿ ? ¡ ! " # % & () ; : . , - _ " [] { } Çç < > ' ° ª \ @ ~ ~ ^

The deliverables and press releases will be presented in **Arial Nova Condensed**.

Arial Nova Condensed

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8.2. Project Website

WHEATBIOME has meticulously developed and consistently maintains its dedicated website, accessible at <https://www.wheatbiome-project.eu/>. The procurement of the URL was diligently undertaken at the project's onset to ensure its sustained availability throughout the project's lifecycle and for an additional two-year period following its conclusion.

The **WHEATBIOME** project website serves as the primary platform for disseminating external information, providing regular updates to all target audiences about the project's activities, milestones, and achievements. The main objective is to present the progress and innovations of **WHEATBIOME** to a wider audience, including members of the public, industry stakeholders, policymakers, and the scientific community.

As the central hub for all communication and social media efforts led by project partners, the website plays a key role in enhancing project visibility and engagement. The strategy to increase website traffic includes building backlinks between partner websites and other related platforms, ensuring information exchange with high visibility. Each project

partner will contribute relevant content, ensuring comprehensive coverage of all project developments.

The **WHEATBIOME** project website contains essential sections such as:

- The project section regarding the objectives, impacts and methodology of the project. (The project, Work packages)
- Resources (Communication materials).
- Knowledge Centre (Deliverables, Publications)
- News

Figure 3: Website Homepage.

8.3. Content management system

The project coordinators, REQUIMTE, have elected Microsoft Teams and SharePoint as the designated software solutions for facilitating remote collaboration and content management within the consortium. Under this arrangement, REQUIMTE has instituted the SharePoint and Teams group, which serves as the central repository for internal project documentation. Access to this online platform is extended to all project partners

and pertinent stakeholders, enabling secure sharing of relevant information, encompassing technical specifications, confidential deliverables, and preliminary project findings.

This repository functions as a platform for consortium members to store, exchange, and collaboratively edit files online, facilitating seamless document creation. Online meetings within the project will primarily be conducted through Microsoft Teams, complemented by material sharing via email for internal communication among **WHEATBIOME** partners.

Additionally, the consortium's internal communication channels feature a dissemination table structured to ensure uniform reporting across all consortium members. This table includes the following categories: Partner, Communication Activity Name, Description, Target Audience, Communication Channel, Outcome Status, Relevant Link, Date, and Project Month.

8.3.1. Content contribution

To enhance our social media profiles and blog, Contactica will request content contributions from project partners as part of the **WHEATBIOME** initiative. This will be facilitated through an Excel file that will be uploaded to SharePoint under the section: WHEATBIOME – WP7 – Editorial Calendar.

Our objective will be to publish at least one blog article each month. Contactica will propose several topics or ideas, and partners will be responsible for writing and submitting the articles. As the work package leader, Contactica will handle the review and necessary adjustments. Once the final article is approved by the authors, it will be scheduled for publication on the **WHEATBIOME's** website and shared on our LinkedIn and Twitter accounts. It is important to note that this content will also be useful for brochures, leaflets, posters, infographics, and potential future press releases.

The editorial calendar will include multiple sheets organized as follows:

- **2024 Calendar:** This sheet will display the current year's calendar with month numbers (M1, M2, M3, etc.) and important highlights. A color legend will be provided on the right side of the sheet.
 - **Blog Articles:** Different colors will indicate the expected dates for publishing articles, approving texts, drafting articles, and submitting required information.
 - **Social Media Posts:** This section will track all scheduled and posted content, allowing us to monitor the frequency and types of posts made.
 - **Relevant Dates:** Significant dates, such as World Environmental Day on June 5, will be highlighted on the calendar to aid in scheduling content and planning campaigns. While these dates will be approximate and may vary depending on deliverables and meetings.
- **Topics and Suggestions:** One sheet will contain a list of potential topics for articles. Partners will be encouraged to propose additional topics that align with their expertise and interests.
- **Blog Post Schedule:** This sheet will track which articles will be produced, who is responsible for each, their upload dates, and their status (e.g., delivered, drafted, scheduled, or published).
- **Blog Post Contributors:** This sheet will serve to track contributions to articles and content creation, ensuring an equitable distribution of efforts among partners.

8.4. Social media

The **WHEATBIOME** project will maintain an active social media presence on X (Twitter) (<https://x.com/wheatbiome>) and LinkedIn (<https://www.linkedin.com/company/wheatbiome-project/>) to ensure widespread dissemination across various age groups and target audiences.

From the project's kick-off meeting, content will be regularly posted on these social media platforms, with updates occurring at least once a week to maximize outreach. The primary goal of utilizing social media will be to drive traffic to the **WHEATBIOME** website while also sharing project-related materials, achievements, upcoming events, and other relevant initiatives.

In the early phase of the project, Contactica will manage the social media accounts to build an audience for future project outcomes and stakeholder events. Regular posts will cover key topics related to **WHEATBIOME's** objectives, attended events, innovations in sustainable agriculture, and other relevant projects in the field.

Social media analytics will be actively monitored to gather data on sources, content performance, and audience engagement. This data will inform future communication efforts, allowing the project team to target specific stakeholders and maximize the reach of **WHEATBIOME's** news and outcomes. Both the final dissemination report and interim reports will incorporate these findings to ensure ongoing optimization of communication strategies. Contactica will oversee the management of social media profiles, with active support from project partners who will be encouraged to engage with and promote the project's online presence whenever possible.

Until this document is completed, the **WHEATBIOME** project social media figures will be tracked and reported regularly.

Here are some best practices to optimize partners' efforts on social media for the **WHEATBIOME** project:

- Tag the project networks in relevant posts:
 - X (Twitter): @wheatbiome
 - LinkedIn: **WHEATBIOME Project**
- Include relevant hashtags like #SustainableAgriculture, #CircularEconomy, and #InnovationInFarming #wheatbiome #microbiome #sustainability
- Add a call to action prompting users to visit the project website by providing the link (e.g., "Visit our website to learn more about this" or "More information on our website").
- Keep track of all communication efforts using a dissemination table accessible to all partners via Sharepoint.

A compilation of pertinent achievements deemed suitable for communication purposes has been outlined below:

- Press release.
- The project website is up and running.
- Stakeholders' list.
- Subscribe to our newsletter.
- Promotional materials.

- Conferences & events attended.
- Newsletters.
- Training workshops.
- Sector engagement workshops.
- Related projects.
- Video.
- Scientific publications.
- General Assembly meetings.
- Final event.
- Participation in the Horizon results booster initiative.

Figure 4 X (Twitter) Profile

Figure 5: LinkedIn Profile

8.5. Printed and digital materials

Brochures and a roll up have been crafted for dissemination within partner networks and at various events such as conferences, exhibitions, workshops, and training sessions. These materials provide comprehensive details about the project's activities, participants, and anticipated outcomes.

Figure 6 Brochure 1.1

Figure 7: Brochure v1.2

Additionally, a single PowerPoint presentation model has been developed to cater to various needs:

- The first one incorporate details about the project's work package structure. This version is intended for presentations to other European projects or initiatives, as well as groups familiar with the structure of Horizon Europe projects.
- The second one, shared internally within the consortium, serves as a supportive resource for presentations at trade fairs, conferences, and other events.

When possible, the communication materials and documents will be adapted in terms of accessibility to be read by voice assistants. This will be pursued by titles and sections in documents, in order to be user-friendly for this kind of voice assistant, as well as in social media

8.6. Newsletters

A regular electronic newsletter will be prepared every six months, featuring project updates, news, interviews, and other content related to **WHEATBIOME**. This newsletter will inform recipients about the project's progress and key achievements in sustainable agriculture and soil health. The contents will also be shared on the **WHEATBIOME** website and may be included in newsletters distributed by partner organizations to their contacts within the agriculture, environmental, and sustainability sectors.

To build the recipients' list, an invitation to subscribe to the newsletter will be published on social media and the **WHEATBIOME** website. Individuals included in the stakeholder list who have given their consent will also be added, in full compliance with GDPR regulations. No personal information will be used without explicit consent. The service provider selected for managing the newsletter distribution will be Mailchimp, ensuring efficient and GDPR-compliant communication.

8.7. Press Releases

Press releases will be created to report significant milestones and progress within the **WHEATBIOME** project as they occur. Project partners will be encouraged to translate and disseminate the press releases to local and national media outlets in their respective countries. Initially written in English, these press releases will be distributed to European press and English-speaking journalists, prioritizing news agencies as primary sources for major media outlets and newspapers.

The inaugural press release, detailing the **WHEATBIOME** project kick-off meeting, will be circulated. Additionally, the first press release with key project details will be sent to partners for dissemination, alongside the announcement of the project's launch.

8.8. Scientific Publications

WHEATBIOME's scientific publications will target a variety of audiences, including the scientific community, educators, industry professionals, and policymakers. These publications will highlight the project's research achievements and technological advancements in sustainable agriculture and soil health. It is anticipated that at least six peer-reviewed scientific papers will be published by the conclusion of the project. Post-project impact will be measured through citation scores and continued engagement with the scientific community.

These scientific publications will be disseminated in accordance with the Open Science practices outlined in Article 17 of the Grant Agreement, titled Communication, Dissemination, Open Science, and Visibility.

8.9. Participation in Conferences, Workshops, and Events

Consortium partners will actively participate in presenting the **WHEATBIOME** project and its outcomes at innovation and networking events, technological fairs, and industry exhibitions. Additionally, they will disseminate project information within other relevant networks and groups, leveraging their existing connections and professional involvement, even if these are not directly related to the project. These activities will enhance the visibility and impact of **WHEATBIOME**, fostering further collaboration and adoption of the project's innovations.

9. COMMUNICATION STRATEGY

At key moments in the **WHEATBIOME** project, it will be essential to communicate findings, progress, and milestones with special emphasis. To effectively spread our message, targeted communication campaigns will be employed. These campaigns may include:

- Press Releases
- Publications in online and printed media
- Special Social Media Campaigns
- Promotion of Events and Workshops

These campaigns will be implemented at specific times throughout the project, utilizing targeted tools and strategies to maximize reach and achieve specific campaign goals.

Below are the steps necessary for effectively communicating different types of project milestones.

9.1. Social Media Campaigns

We expect to launch three social media campaigns in the second year of the project.

1. Wheatbiome Principles

- **Objective:** Promote the core values and principles of sustainable wheat farming and research innovations.
- **Format:** A series of dynamic social media posts on LinkedIn and X (formerly Twitter). Each post include concise text, accompanied by an eye-catching visual or infographic. The posts focus on sustainability, microbiome research, and farmer engagement. The campaign took place during three months, with 3 to 4 posts per month.
- **Content:** Each post highlight key historical, current, and numerical data about wheat, as well as educational information related to the **WHEATBIOME** project. Audiences were encouraged to share and discuss the content, with a call-to-action directing them to the project's blog for deeper insights.

2. #WheatBiomesInnovations

- **Objective:** Highlight innovative research findings and technological advancements from the **WHEATBIOME** project.
- **Format:** A series of 8 engaging infographics, each consisting of 5 to 7 slides, will be released bi-weekly. The first infographic is expected to be published at the beginning of the second year of the project.
- **Content:** Each infographic will focus on a specific innovation or research finding, encouraging audiences to engage with the content. These infographics will be paired with blog articles that provide in-depth information, published one week after each infographic. This strategy aims to foster awareness and interest while encouraging sharing among audiences.

3. Meet the WheatBiome Team

- **Objective:** Introduce project partners and key team members to the public.
- **Timeline:** Every Tuesday
- **Content Requirements:** Each partner will need to provide the following to Contactica:
 - An abstract (maximum 500 characters, including spaces) about their organization and role in the project.
 - A quote (maximum 300 characters) discussing their enthusiasm and motivation for contributing to **WHEATBIOME**.
 - A photo showcasing their team members or facilities, ideally in a wheat-themed or sustainable context.
 - A link to their organization's website.
 - Their Twitter and LinkedIn profiles, including those of individuals quoted, for tagging and cross-promotion purposes.

9.2. Other Relevant Campaigns

1. Sustainable Wheat Production Awareness Campaign

- **Objective:** Raise awareness about the importance of sustainable wheat farming practices and how the **WHEATBIOME** project contributes to enhancing crop quality and resilience.
- **Target Audience:** Farmers, agricultural professionals, food industry stakeholders, and policymakers.
- **Actions:**
 - **Social Media Series:** Create a series of informative posts that highlight sustainable practices in wheat production, including soil health management and biodiversity protection. Use visuals and data to showcase the impact of these practices on crop yield and quality. Hashtags like #SustainableWheat, #WheatBiomes, and #FoodSecurity can be utilized.
 - **Press Release:** Issue a press release announcing the launch of the **WHEATBIOME** project, detailing its objectives and the

expected contributions to sustainable agriculture in Europe. Target local and national media outlets in the agriculture sector.

- **Educational Webinar:** Organize a webinar featuring project partners discussing the challenges and innovations in sustainable wheat farming. This event can provide a platform for knowledge sharing and encourage collaboration among stakeholders.

2. Biodiversity in Agriculture Campaign

- **Objective:** Highlight the significance of biodiversity in wheat farming and its role in enhancing climate resilience and sustainability.
- **Target Audience:** Environmental organizations, agricultural scientists, policymakers, and the general public.
- **Actions:**
 - **Biodiversity Day Event:** Host an event on International Day for Biological Diversity, showcasing the **WHEATBIOME** project's efforts to protect and promote biodiversity in wheat crops. Include presentations, workshops, and demonstrations of biodiversity-friendly practices.
 - **Social Media Challenge:** Launch a challenge encouraging farmers and community members to share their biodiversity initiatives in wheat farming using the hashtag #WheatBiomesBiodiversity. This could include photos of diverse crop rotations, cover crops, or pollinator habitats.
 - **Informative Brochures:** Develop brochures that explain the importance of biodiversity in agriculture, featuring success stories from the **WHEATBIOME** project. Distribute these materials at agricultural fairs and conferences.

3. Healthy Food Systems Campaign

- **Objective:** Promote the role of wheat in healthy diets and the **WHEATBIOME** project's commitment to delivering nutritious products through sustainable practices.
- **Target Audience:** Consumers, health professionals, nutritionists, and

food industry stakeholders.

- **Actions:**

- **Nutrition Workshops:** Conduct workshops in schools and community centers focusing on the nutritional benefits of wheat and how sustainable practices enhance food quality. Include cooking demonstrations using wheat-based products.
- **Social Media Awareness Posts:** Create posts that educate consumers about the health benefits of wheat and the importance of sustainable food production. Use visually appealing graphics and statistics to engage the audience, employing hashtags like #HealthyWheat, #WheatBiomes, and #SustainableFood.
- **Partnership with Nutritionists:** Collaborate with nutritionists to develop content that highlights the role of wheat in balanced diets, sharing recipes and tips for incorporating wheat products into daily meals. Distribute this content through newsletters and social media channels.

10. INDICATORS AND TARGETS

The attainment of defined targets outlined in Table 3 will serve as the benchmark for evaluating the successful implementation of the Dissemination and Communication Plan upon the project's conclusion.

11. LEVELS OF DISSEMINATION

The choice of communication methods and media will be tailored to accommodate the diverse geographic reach of key target groups.

11.1. European Level – European Commission

Regular updates on project outcomes will be provided to the European Commission through periodic reporting, including the mid-term review and updates to project documentation. Collaboration opportunities with other ongoing projects for dissemination activities will be explored, and adjustments to current work will be proposed as necessary.

11.2. International Level – Industry, Scientific Community

Relevant international organizations will be informed about the project's findings. Scientific insights will be translated into practical data, regulations, and recommendations. Electronic resources will be directly shared with designated organizations and stakeholders to raise public awareness.

Technical publications, conferences, and workshops, both nationally and internationally, as well as industry meetings and participation in industrial forums, will be utilized to disseminate knowledge to both research and industrial audiences.

12. THE DISSEMINATION OPEN ACCESS

Open access (OA) refers to the practice of providing online access to scientific information that is free of charge to the end-user and reusable. 'Scientific' refers to all academic disciplines. In the context of research and innovation, 'scientific information' can mean:

- Peer-reviewed scientific research articles (published in scholarly journals).
- Research data (data underlying publications, curated data and/or raw data).

12.1. Peer-reviewed scientific research articles

Open access to scientific publications means free online access for any user. Although there are no legally binding definitions of 'access' or 'open access' in this context, authoritative definitions of open access appear in key political declarations including:

- the 2002 [Budapest Declaration](#)
- the 2003 [Berlin Declaration](#)

Under these definitions, 'access' includes not only basic elements - the right to read, download and print – but also **the right to copy, distribute, search, link, crawl and mine.**

The main route to open access is:

Open access publishing / 'gold' open access - an article is immediately published in open access mode. In this model, the payment of publication costs is shifted away from subscribing readers. The most common business model is

based on one-off payments by authors. These costs, often referred to as Article Processing Charges (APCs) are usually borne by the researcher's university or research institute or the agency funding the research. In other cases, the costs of open access publishing are covered by subsidies or other funding models.

In the context of research funding, **open access requirements do not imply an obligation to publish results**. The decision to publish is entirely up to the grant beneficiaries. **Open access becomes an issue *only if* publication is chosen as a means of dissemination**.

Moreover, open access does not affect the decision to exploit research results commercially, e.g. through patenting.

12.2. Open access to research data

Open access to **research data** refers to the right to access and reuse digital research data under the terms and conditions set out in the Grant Agreement.

Research data refers to **information**, in particular facts or numbers, collected to be examined and considered as a basis for reasoning, discussion, or calculation.

In a research context, examples of data include statistics, results of experiments, measurements, observations resulting from fieldwork, survey results, interview recordings and images. **The focus is on research data that is available in digital form**. Users can normally access, mine, exploit, reproduce and disseminate openly accessible research data free of charge.

Mandate on open access to publications:

Each beneficiary must ensure open access to all peer-reviewed scientific publications relating to its results.

To meet this requirement, beneficiaries must, at the very least, **ensure that any scientific peer-reviewed publications can be read online, downloaded and printed**. Since any further rights - such as the right to copy, distribute, search, link, crawl and mine - make publications more useful, beneficiaries should make every effort to provide

as many of these options as possible.

Peer-reviewed publications are **those assessed by other scholars**. Peer review is typically, though not exclusively, organised by the journal or publisher to which an article or manuscript is submitted. However, new approaches are expected to become more prevalent in years to come. The dominant type of scientific publication is the journal article. Grant beneficiaries are also strongly encouraged to provide open access to other types of scientific publications including:

- Monographs
- Books
- Conference proceedings
- Grey literature (informally published written material not controlled by scientific publishers, e.g., reports)

The open-access mandate comprises 2 steps:

1. Depositing publications in repositories
2. Providing open access to them.

13. METHODOLOGY

The following internal and external communication actions will be carried out throughout the **WHEATBIOME** project and beyond, ensuring the successful and efficient dissemination of outcomes to project partners, stakeholders, and broader audiences.

13.1. Internal Communication

Effective internal communication is crucial for seamless information sharing and for achieving the project's goals in the **WHEATBIOME** initiative. This will be facilitated through regular meetings, conference calls, and consortium gatherings. The **WHEATBIOME** project will utilize Microsoft Teams to enhance collaboration and coordination among project partners. The communication and dissemination plan will be periodically updated with input from all partners, ensuring alignment with the project's progress. To streamline access to project materials, a dedicated Google Drive space will be established for internal sharing. This platform will contain up-to-date project progress reports, meeting minutes, and other relevant documents, all accessible through secure

login credentials.

13.2. External Communication

The **WHEATBIOME** project team will utilize a variety of platforms to publicize its work and disseminate key findings, including academic journals, conferences, industry exhibitions, workshops, agricultural and sustainability associations, and media outlets. The project's results will be shared through comprehensive reports, articles, and scientific publications. Public access to all scientific outputs and communications will be encouraged, especially within the scientific community and agricultural industry. Furthermore, open access to peer-reviewed papers will foster collaboration, transparency, and the further adoption of **WHEATBIOME'S** innovations in sustainable wheat production and ecosystem management.

This structured approach to both internal and external communication will ensure that **WHEATBIOME's** findings are effectively shared with relevant audiences, contributing to the broader dissemination of sustainable agricultural practices and technologies.

14. EXPLOITATION STRATEGY

14.1. Methodology and procedure

In order to organize the creation of the exploitation plan, an ex-post facto methodology will be followed according to the methods developed by C. R. Kothari. (KOTHARI, 1990). For exploitation, descriptive research will be followed as it is the description of the state of affairs as it exists at present. The methods of research utilized in descriptive research are survey methods of all kinds, including comparative and correlational methods.

Based on this method, **Contactica** has developed a methodology to be applied in exploitation, as a whole, to provide the best overview of **WHEATBIOME's** results at the end of the project. The methodology is presented in the figure below:

Figure 8: Exploitation Methodology - Source: Contactica

Each component of this methodology will also come with a set of tools adapted to the preparation of each segment of the exploitation strategies. To give a thorough image of **WHEATBIOME’s** results and update the KERs, **Contactica** will use a series of tools dedicated to unlock the potential of the project. Each tool will be presented in the relevant

deliverable set in the Grant Agreement. (SWOT, CANVAS, 4Ps...)

As exploitation is a work of all partners, **Contactica** will send regularly during the project an Exploitation Questionnaire, completed with Exploitation or IP Workshops (see figures below), during the General Assemblies or online if necessary to keep track on **WHEATBIOME’s** results, linked to other WP advancement. The work realized will be also included in the technical reports dedicated to the WP7.

Figure 9: WHEATBIOME Exploitation Questionnaire Main Page

Figure 10: WHEATBIOME Exploitation Workshop PowerPoint

14.2. Key Exploitable Results and IPR Management

In the proposal-stage of the project, the consortium came together to build a list of Exploitable Results and possible exploitation strategy that are included in the table below. The protection of the exploitable results has also been anticipated for each KER. During the course of the project, they will be finetuned and assessed in order to be included in the deliverable D7.5 “Exploitation Plan – First version” in M32 and D7.6 “Exploitation Plan – Final version” in M48.

Table 4: WHEATBIOME Exploitation Plan

	BACKGROUND IN USE	EXPLOITABLE RESULTS	EXPLOITATIO N STRATEGY	IP PROTECTION
REQUIMITE	Experts in in vitro interaction studies of the human microbiome	New molecular and cell models for microbiota studies in bio-availability & -accessibility	Further internal, collaborative research and replication activities	Confidentiality, Copyright
		New knowledge on the oral microbiota contribution for unpleasant taste perception	(Application of new models and knowledge to other projects); scientific publications	
UPORTO	Experts in agronomy, edaphology, microbiology, ecotoxicology and consumer's evaluation of agri-food products	New knowledge on the cross-talk between wheat microbiome, (a)biotic factors and wheat quality New data on sensory profiling of novel fermented products	Scientific Publications; further internal and collaborative research	Copyright; confidentiality
UVIGO	Expertise in Nutrition and Food studies and analysis	Know-how on extraction methods for bioactive compounds analysis.	Scientific publications; networking and future joint research; and training of PhD and postdoctoral students	Copyright; confidentiality
		New standardization procedures for wheat nutritional profiles		

UVEG	Expert in fermentation processes and innovative food processing technologies	New wheat-isolated microbial cultures for biotech applications	Patent licensing / Spin-off for these isolated microbials	Patent
		New knowledge on fermentation processes and recycle of wheat by-products	Scientific publications, more internal/joint research (use of new methods in other projects)	Copyright; confidentiality
IBPRIS	Expertise in microbial technology, fermentation and food safety assessment	Know-how on the use of wheat by-products and impact of fermentation in feed production	Further internal research, PhD/Postdoc training, and scientific publications	Confidentiality; copyright
CONTACTICA	Expert in LCA and LCC assessments.	Know-how on conducting LCA on multiple agricultural scenarios and case studies	Replication activities & joint research (LCA & LCC services for other agro-food companies)	Trade secret

WUR	Expertise in metabolomics and proteomics analysis, especially in plant allergens and polyphenolics	New knowledge on processing methods reducing levels of immunogenic peptides in wheat	Scientific publications, internal or collaborative research, replication activities (use of new skills on other food types)	Copyright; Confidentiality
SGGW	Expert in poultry health studies	New knowledge on the impact of fermented feed on poultry health and quality of products	Scientific publications, further internal or collaborative research	Copyright; Confidentiality
		New diets that improve poultry health and quality of products	Patent licensing / Spin-off of the new poultry diets	Patent
NMS	Expert in designing and conducting clinical studies for microbiota evaluation	New knowledge on the interference of fermented product with human microbiota	Scientific publications, further internal or collaborative research	Copyright; Confidentiality

UVMB	Expertise in risk assessment and communication in food system actors & consumers	New knowledge on risk perception of food system stakeholders about microbiomes and communication approaches	Replication activities & joint research (use of risk assessment in other projects), scientific publications	Copyright; Confidentiality
EDAGRI	Expertise in communication, dissemination and organization of international events in the agro-food field	Know-how of new hybrid approaches and multimedia tactics for international events	Replication activities (application on new methodology on other projects or countries)	Confidentiality
ART21	Experts in agriculture data science and development of decision support systems	New knowledge on artificial intelligence analysis architecture and analytical algorithms	More internal/joint research & replication activities (use of DSS and APP in other fields/countries)	Trade secret; Copyright

ISANATUR	Expertise in manufacturing of food products, including functional foods	New knowledge on fermentation and processing techniques for food production	Replication activities (application of new methodology on other products or projects), further internal/collaborative research	Trade secret
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14.3. Exploitation Planning

The effort to generate revenue streams from project outputs will be significantly enhanced by the active involvement of the technology transfer offices of academic partners together with innovation specialist partner **Contactica**.

After the start of the Exploitation task 7.5 in M19, **Contactica** will, in collaboration with all the involved partners, set an Exploitation Planning to anticipate the post-funding period of the project.

Figure 11: WHEATBIOME Expected results and measures at proposal stage

The Exploitation Plan serves as a map of where the project is heading and what means the consortium is taking to reach these results. This section serves as an introduction to the **WHEATBIOME** project strategy and methodology that will be followed starting M19,

until the end of the project. All sections of this section will be updated in the exploitation deliverables as well as the methodology if required.